

Use of 2-Hydroxy 4-Ethoxyacetophenone Oxime (HEAO) as Analytical Reagent: Gravimetric Determination of Copper

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2-Hydroxy 4-ethoxyacetophenone oxime (HEAO) has been used as a reagent for gravimetric estimation of copper and for its separation from other ions. The buff precipitation of the copper ion by the reagent is complete between pH 2.5 to 9.0, and after drying at 120° the composition of the precipitate corresponds to $Cu(C_{10}H_{12}O_5N)_2$. It is also observed that by proper control of pH and by using suitable masking agents, it is possible to estimate copper in presence of other interfering ions.

MANY oximes have been used as analytical reagents for gravimetric determination of a number of metal ions. The well known examples belonging to different oxime series Salicyldoxime¹⁻³, Resacetophenone oxime^{4,5} and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime⁶⁻⁹ have already been reported as analytical reagents for copper.

The present work with the reagent (HEAO) was undertaken with the intention to introduce new ligand for the gravimetric determination of copper. The copper chelate with resacetophenone oxime is soluble in alcohol⁵ and does not settle down⁴ while the copper chelate with HEAO is insoluble in alcohol and the reagent is soluble in 40% alcohol and hence excess of the reagent which precipitates can be easily washed out by 40% alcohol. The reagent precipitates copper quantitatively at pH range 2.5 to 9. Cations like Zinc(II), Magnesium(II), Cadmium(II), Strontium(II), Manganese(II), Aluminium(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) are found not to interfere at pH range 3.00 to 4.00.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Stock solutions of Cu(II) (0.05M) was prepared by dissolving $CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ in double distilled water and was standardised by conventional methods. An ethanolic solution of ligand (1%) was employed and the pH was adjusted using acetate buffer.

2-Hydroxy 4-ethoxyacetophenone oxime: The reagent¹⁰ (m.p. 48°-49°) was prepared using ethyl iodide, resacetophenone and anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone, and its oxime by the reaction with hydroxyl amine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in dilute ethanol. It was crystallised from petroleum ether, colourless needless m.p. 95° [N Calc. 7.2%, found 7.08%].

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Determination of copper: A solution containing known amount of Cu(II) was diluted to about 200 ml and pH was adjusted using acetate buffer. The solution was warmed to 60°-70° and 1% ethanolic solution of the reagent was added with constant stirring followed by about 10% excess to ensure complete precipitation. The precipitate was digested on water-bath (60°-70°) for 30 min. It was filtered while hot through sintered glass crucibles (G-4) and washed with hot water (60°-70°). The precipitate was finally washed with 40% alcohol. The precipitate was dried at 120°, to constant weight, weighed as $Cu(C_{10}H_{12}O_5N)_2$. Copper bis-chelate is insoluble in alcohol, ether, acetic acid, carbon tetrachloride but it is soluble in chloroform and sparingly soluble in hot benzene. It has been found that copper can be quantitatively determined in the pH range 3.0 to 9.0. The conversion factor of copper/copper chelate is 0.1407. The results of some of the estimations are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Cu(II) AT pH = 3.5

Sr. no.	Cu(II) taken, mg.	Cu(II) complex, mg.	Cu(II) found, mg.	Error %
1	7.85	55.7	7.84	-0.12
2	15.71	112.0	15.76	+0.31
3	23.56	167.9	23.62	+0.25
4	31.42	223.6	31.47	+0.15
5	39.27	279.5	39.32	+0.12
6	47.13	334.5	47.06	-0.14
7	62.84	447.8	62.99	+0.18

Determination of copper in presence of other ions: Since cations Zn(II), Cd(II), Sr(II), Mg(II), Mn(II) and Al(III) were not found to give any colour formation or insoluble chelate, Cu(II) can be determined in presence of these cations by working at pH 3-6.

maximum error being $\pm 0.82\%$. The anions like chloride, bromide, sulphate, tartrate, citrate do not interfere in the estimation of copper.

The reagent reacts with Co(II) at pH 5.5 giving orange yellow coloured ppt., with Ni(II) at pH 5.0 giving green coloured ppt and with Fe(III) at pH 2.6 giving blue-violet colouration.

Since Co(II) and Ni(II) start precipitating at considerable higher pH, Cu(II) can be determined in presence of these ions by working at controlled pH.

Presence of Fe(III) interferences during the determination of Cu(II); however the determination was carried out by sequestering the Fe(III) by potassium tartrate.

TABLE 2—GRAVIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF CU(II) AT pH 3.5 IN PRESENCE OF OTHER IONS

Cu(II) taken 15.71 mg				
Sr. no.	Metal Ion	Amount added, mg.	Cu(II) found, mg.	Error %
1	Cd(II)	14.0	15.76	+0.31
2	Al(III)	6.75	15.84	+0.82
3	Zn(II)	8.1	15.81	+0.63
4	Mn(II)	6.87	15.70	-0.06
5	Co(II)	7.2	15.70	-0.06
6	Ni(II)	7.6	15.76	+0.31
7	Sr(II)	10.5	15.79	+0.51
8	Mg(II)	7.3	15.73	+0.12
9	Fe(III)	8.0	15.79	+0.51

Structure of copper chelate: The copper chelate was analysed to the carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content to determine the composition. The metal content was determined by standard analytical method. [Found : C, 53.35; H, 5.2; N, 6.1; Cu, 13.8%. Calculated C, 53.10; H, 5.3; N, 6.2; Cu, 14.10%]. The composition of chelate corresponds to formulae $Cu(C_{10}H_{12}O_3)_2$, metal ligand ratio is 1 : 2. The molecular weight determined cryoscopically using camphor as solvent showed the chelate to be monomeric, i.e. the chelate could be represented by ML_2 . The 1 : 2 stoichiometric confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation. For this the chelate was extracted in chloroform and the absorption was measured. The maximum was found to be 33% of M/M^{+2} giving 1 : 2 composition.

The magnetic susceptibility of this chelate was determined at room temperature on a Guoy balance. The magnetic moment calculated from the susceptibility is found to be 1.79 on the basis of "Spin-spin" value, the chelate is assigned one unpaired electron. From the number of unpaired electrons the structure is considered to be squareplanar. On the basis of above results the following structure is suggested for copper chelate.

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